

DNA binding/cleavage studies of known hexanuclear/trinuclear copper(II) complexes in presence of standard activators[†]

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Abstract : The polynuclear copper(II) complexes of types $[\text{Cu}_6\text{Na}_4(\text{NTA})_2(\mu\text{-O})_2(\text{bpy})_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{NO}_3)_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2(\text{bpy})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (**2**) (bpy = 2,2'-bipyridyl, H_3NTA = nitrilotriacetic acid and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ = oxalate) recently reported by us, have been allowed to interact with calf thymus DNA. Their DNA binding properties are studied using absorption and emission spectral titrations. These complexes cleave supercoiled pBR322 DNA to nicked circular DNA under physiological conditions. Studies using standard radical scavengers suggest the involvement of hydroxyl radicals in the oxidative cleavage of DNA.

Keywords : Polynuclear, copper(II) complexes, nuclease property, oxidative cleavage, gel electrophoresis.

Introduction

Synthetic metal complexes showing nuclease property are considered of worth owing to their probable applications as therapeutic agents and also usefulness in genomic research¹⁻⁴. Metal complexes are particularly attractive systems to study because they are usually cationic, which ensures their attraction to DNA. Furthermore, the fact that, in most complexes the metal holds ligating organic molecules which by shape and surface could be featured in such a way that can allow the formation of hydrogen bond or can provide $\pi\text{-}\pi$ interactions. Such forces may enable to interact with the complementary partner of nucleotide skeleton of DNA. Complexes of redox active and biologically relevant metal ion like copper(II) had been recently exploited in the cleavage of DNA and also such ions show affinity with nucleic acid bases⁵. The redox property of the metal center as well as dioxygen molecules are utilized to generate reactive oxygen species that can damage DNA by direct strand scission or base modification⁵. The most well-known and best studied example is $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline)⁶⁻⁹. In this context, it is worth to mention that multinuclear metal ion are often found in natural nucleases and they may demonstrate synergistic effects in

O_2 activation and DNA recognition^{3,7,9}. Thus, it was thought to investigate the behavior of presently reported complexes of types **1** and **2** containing six and three copper centres in their skeleton beside several other groups which can assist the stabilization of interaction of metal complexes with calf thymus (CT) DNA. Their bindings with DNA are monitored using UV-Vis spectral titrations and competitive binding experiments using emission spectral titrations. Complexes **1** and **2** cleave DNA without the presence of any activator. This feature is considered valuable as it brings out metal complexes to be potential candidate as chemotherapeutic. The cleavage of DNA using variable concentrations of the complexes have been performed on a pBR322 DNA. For comparative studies, DNA cleavage in the presence of selected radical scavengers have been carried out.

Results and discussion

Complexes **1** and **2** had been reported by us earlier¹⁰ as shown in Scheme 1. The selectivity of nitrilotriacetic acid (H_3NTA) as a building block has been made in view of resemblance of its coordination sites with the coordination sites found in structural framework of a protein like concanavalin¹¹. However, use of planar bipyridyl

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

Scheme 1. Synthetic scheme of complexes 1 and 2.

was selected owing to its good binding propensity with DNA¹². Since, DNA binding and cleavage studies were carried out in aqueous medium, UV-Vis spectra of complexes 1 and 2 were recorded in DMSO/water (v/v, 1 : 10) mixture. UV-Vis spectra of complexes reveals that structures of the complexes retained in DMSO/water mixture.

UV-Vis absorption studies for the binding of complexes 1 and 2 with CT-DNA :

As reported earlier¹³ that binding mode of DNA with metal complexes could be examined using electronic absorption spectroscopy as an effective tool, the present

complexes are also titrated with DNA using UV-Vis spectral data. In general, intercalation of a complex with DNA results in a hypochromic red shift in its absorption band. This may occur due to strong stacking interactions between aromatic chromophore of the complexes and the base pairs of the DNA. The copper(II) complexes can bind to the double-stranded DNA in different modes on the basis of their structure, charge and type of ligands present in their structural framework. On increasing the concentration of CT-DNA, the hypochromicity increases in the ligand-centred (LC) band of the complexes 1 and 2 as depicted in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. In order to compare the binding strength of the complexes with CT-

Fig. 1. UV-Vis absorption spectra of [Complex 1] = 10 μM in the absence and in presence of increasing amounts of DNA = 0–50 μM . Arrow shows the absorbance changes upon increasing DNA concentrations.

Fig. 2. UV-Vis absorption spectra of [Complex 2] = 10 μM in the absence and in presence of increasing amounts of DNA = 0-50 μM. Arrow shows the absorbance changes upon increasing DNA concentrations.

DNA, the intrinsic binding constant K_b was obtained as ratio of slope to the intercept from the plots of $[DNA]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ vs $[DNA]$. The calculated K_b values of $3.5 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $1.6 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for complexes 1 and 2 respectively showed that there is a stronger binding of complex 1 with DNA as compared to the binding of complex 2. It could be considered in view of the report that polynuclear complexes can enhance their affinity to anionic DNA, suggesting a synergistic effect of the Cu^{II} centers¹⁴.

Competitive binding with ethidium bromide (EB) :

The ability of a metal complex to affect the fluorescence intensity of EB-DNA adduct is a reliable tool for the measurement of its affinity towards DNA. The intensity of emitted light from EB is found to be normally quenched by surrounding water molecule¹⁵. However, in the presence of DNA, owing to strong intercalation between adjacent DNA base pairs, intensity of emission from EB-DNA adduct is enhanced. However, the intensity of emission from EB-DNA adduct again decreases upon its binding with complex. The emission spectra of EB-DNA system in presence and absence of copper complexes 1 and 2 are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The addition

of complexes to DNA pretreated with EB shows appreciable reductions in emission intensity. On the addition of 5 μM of complex 1 to 10 μM of CT DNA pretreated with EB, ~85% displacement of ethidium bromide was observed. However, ~50% of ethidium bromide were displaced at same concentrations of complex 2. The quenching plots of I_0/I vs $[\text{Complex}]/[\text{DNA}]$ (the inset of Figs. 5 and 6) are in good agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation. Stern-Volmer quenching constants (K_{sv}) were calculated to be 1.2 and 0.6 for complex 1 and complex 2 respectively.

Chemical nuclease activity :

The cleavage of DNA activated by the complexes 1 and 2 have been studied using a plasmid relaxation assay to monitor the conversion of circular supercoiled pBR322 DNA (SC) to its nicked circular (NC) form by gel electrophoresis. In order to assess the chemical nuclease activity of the complexes (1 and 2) for DNA strand scission, pBR322 DNA was incubated with varying concentration of complex 1 (10-60 μM) and complex 2 (10-70 μM) in a medium of 50 mM Tris-HCl/NaCl buffer (pH 7.2). The cleavage reaction were monitored by the gel

Fig. 3. Emission spectra of EB bound to DNA in the absence and in the presence of, [Complex 1] 0–5 μM , [EB] 10 μM , [DNA] 10 μM . Arrow shows changes in the emission intensity upon addition of increasing concentration of the complex.

Fig. 4. Emission spectra of EB bound to DNA in the absence and in the presence of, [Complex 2] 0–5 μM , [EB] 10 μM , [DNA] 10 μM . Arrow shows changes in the emission intensity upon addition of increasing concentration of the complex.

electrophoresis. When pBR322 DNA is subjected to electrophoresis, relatively fast migration will be observed for

the intact supercoiled form (form I). If scission occurs on one strand (nicking), the supercoiled form will relax to

generate a slower-moving nicked form (form II). If both strands are cleaved, a linear form (form III) that migrates between form I and form II will be generated. The cleavage pattern of complexes 1 and 2 observed is shown in Figs. 5 and 6 respectively. Although both compounds converted form I (supercoiled) DNA to form II (nicked, relaxed form), higher concentration of complex 2 (70 μM) is required in comparison to complex 1 (40 μM) in order to cleave the DNA completely, as evident from Figs. 5 and 6 respectively.

Fig. 5. The cleavage patterns of the agarose gel electrophoresis for pBR322 plasmid DNA (300 ng) by complex 1. Lane 1, DNA; Lane 2, 10 μM complex + DNA; Lane 3, 20 μM complex + DNA; Lane 4, 30 μM complex + DNA; Lane 5, 40 μM complex + DNA; Lane 6, 50 μM complex + DNA; Lane 7, 60 μM complex + DNA.

Fig. 6. The cleavage patterns of the agarose gel electrophoresis for pBR322 plasmid DNA (300 ng) by complex 2. Lane 1, DNA; Lane 2, 10 μM complex + DNA; Lane 3, 20 μM complex + DNA; Lane 4, 30 μM complex + DNA; Lane 5, 40 μM complex + DNA; Lane 6, 50 μM complex + DNA; Lane 7, 60 μM complex + DNA; Lane 8, 70 μM complex + DNA.

DNA cleavage in presence of minor and major groove binding agents :

To explore the DNA cleavage mechanism of complexes with supercoiled plasmid pBR322 DNA gel electrophoresis study with DNA was carried out in presence of minor groove binding agent like 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) and major groove binding agent like methyl green (MG)¹⁶. The supercoiled DNA was treated separately with DAPI and MG prior to the addition of the complexes. The pattern shown in Fig. 7 clearly demonstrate that in case of complex 1 neither DAPI nor methyl

Fig. 7. Agarose gel electrophoresis pattern for the cleavage pattern of pBR322 plasmid DNA (300 ng) by complex 1 (50 μM) and complex 2 (70 μM). Lane 1, DNA control; Lane 2, DNA + metal complex 2, Lane 3, DNA + metal complex 2 + methyl green (2.5 μL of 0.01 mg/mL solution); Lane 4, DNA + metal complex + DAPI (8 μM), Lane 5, DNA + metal complex 1; Lane 3, DNA + metal complex 2 + methyl green (2.5 μL of 0.01 mg/mL solution); Lane 4, DNA + metal complex 1 + DAPI (8 μM)

green affected the DNA cleavage activity, suggesting that neither major nor minor grooves of DNA are the preferred reacting sites for the complex. Thus, complex 1 may interact directly with exterior phosphates of DNA via electrostatic attraction. The cationic core of complex 1 in aqueous solution could bind to the anionic phosphate backbone of DNA by electrostatic attraction. Such general affinity may enhance local concentration of complex 1 around DNA¹⁷ and enhance the DNA cleavage activity. However, in case of complex 2 DNA cleavage was not affected by methyl green but was affected by DAPI, suggesting that complex 2 binds at the minor grooves of DNA. Thus, the experiment suggested that hexanuclear Cu^{II} complex owing to its multinuclearity possesses higher metal containing surface area and allows the first hand possible electrostatic interactions.

DNA cleavage mechanism :

Additionally, ROS generated during the interaction between copper complexes and dioxygen or redox reagents are believed to be a major cause of DNA damage¹⁸. In order to explore further information about active oxygen species responsible for DNA damage, DNA cleavage was carried out in the presence of hydroxyl radical scavengers like DMSO, EtOH and singlet oxygen quencher (NaN_3) in a medium of 50 mM Tris-HCl/NaCl buffer (pH 7.2). As observed from the electrophoretic pattern shown in Fig. 8, in case of complex 1, on addition of singlet oxygen scavenger, sodium azide (Lane 2), the cleavage efficiency decreases significantly revealing that $^1\text{O}_2$ -derived species might serve as the activated intermediates responsible for the DNA cleavage. The involvement of

Fig. 8. Agarose gel electrophoresis pattern for the cleavage pattern of pBR322 plasmid DNA (300 ng) by complex 1 (50 μM) and 2 (70 μM). Lane 1, DNA control; Lane 2, DNA + metal complex 1 + NaN_3 (0.4 mM); Lane 3, DNA + metal complex 1 + DMSO (0.4 mM); Lane 4, DNA + metal complex 1 + D_2O (70%); Lane 5, DNA + metal complex + NaN_3 (0.4 mM); Lane 6, DNA + metal complex + DMSO (0.4 mM); Lane 7, DNA + metal complex + ethanol (0.4 mM); Lane 8, DNA + metal complex + D_2O (70%) respectively.

$^1\text{O}_2$ is also established by the significant enhancement of the cleavage activity in D_2O (Lane 4), where the lifetime of $^1\text{O}_2$ is notably longer than that in water. Upon addition of standard hydroxyl radical scavenger, DMSO (Lane 3) the DNA cleavage was significantly reduced indicating that the hydroxyl radicals are involved in the cleavage process. Thus, free radicals participate in the oxidation of the deoxyribose moiety, followed by hydrolytic cleavage of the sugar phosphate backbone in the absence of the scavengers. These results suggest that the DNA strand scission reaction caused by these complexes involve various diffusible oxygen intermediate species (hydroxyl radical or singlet oxygen) are involved and hence a simple diffusible radical mechanism is applicable in the way as reported earlier¹⁹. However, complex 2, in presence of sodium azide, could not inhibit cleavage (Lane 5) significantly, when D_2O was added to reaction mixture as there was no enhancement in the cleavage process (Lane 8), which supports that in cleavage process no singlet oxygen species is involved. However, presence of hydroxyl radical scavengers DMSO (Lane 6), EtOH (Lane 7) showed inhibition of the cleavage activity, suggesting involvement of diffusible hydroxyl radical as the reactive species leading to strand scission.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Reagents of A.R. purity were purchased from standard commercial sources (Sigma-Aldrich, Merck) and used without further purification. The UV-Vis and luminescence spectra of complexes were recorded using Shimadzu UV-1601 and Perkin-Elmer LS 45 spectrofluorometer.

However, the precursors, $\text{Cu}(\text{bpy})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ are prepared using the reported procedure by Sen *et al.*²⁰.

Synthesis of complexes :

Complexes 1 and 2 were synthesized using procedure reported earlier¹⁰.

Absorption titration :

The binding of the complexes 1 and 2 with DNA was measured in a Na-phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.2). As normally, the absorption ratio at 260 nm and 280 nm of CT DNA solutions was measured as 1.9 : 1, supporting that used DNA is sufficiently free of protein. The concentration of DNA was then determined by UV-Visible absorbance using the molar absorption coefficient ($6600 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at 260 nm²¹. The absorption titration of 1 and 2 (10 μM) in Na-phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) containing 2% DMSO was carried out against CT DNA solution and changes in absorption spectra were monitored. The concentration of metal complexes was kept constant at 10 μM in each titration while the concentration of CT DNA was varied within 0–50 μM . An equal quantity of CT DNA was also added to the reference solution to eliminate the absorption by DNA. From the absorption data, the intrinsic binding constant K_b was calculated from a plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ using the equation :

$$[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f) = [\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f) + [K_b(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f)]^{-1}$$

where, $[\text{DNA}]$ represents the concentration of DNA in base pairs. The apparent absorption coefficients ϵ_a , ϵ_f and ϵ_b correspond to $A_{\text{obsd.}}/[\text{Cu}]$, the extinction coefficient for the free copper(II) complex and extinction coefficient for the copper(II) complex in the fully bound form, respectively²². K_b was calculated as the ratio of slope to the intercept.

Competitive binding studies :

Relative binding of copper complexes to CT DNA was also studied by fluorescence spectroscopy using ethidium bromide (EB) bound to CT DNA in a Na phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.2). In a typical experiment, 20 μL of CT-DNA solution ($A_{260} = 2.0$) was added to 2.0 mL of EB in buffer solution (pH 7.2) and the fluorescence intensity was measured upon excitation at λ_{max} 510 nm; maximum emission was observed at 600 nm. The concentration of the complex were increased by addition of aliquots from a 0.1 mM stock solution until no change

in fluorescence intensity occur. Stern-Volmer quenching constant was calculated using following equation²³,

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{sv}r,$$

where, I_0 and I are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of complexes, respectively, K_{sv} is a linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant and r is the ratio of total concentration of complex to that of DNA. The value of K_{sv} is given by the ratio of slope to intercept in a plot of I_0/I versus $[\text{Complex}]/[\text{DNA}]$.

DNA cleavage study :

Cleavage experiments of supercoiled pBR322 DNA (300 ng) in presence of complex **1** (10–60 μM) and complex **2** (10–70 μM) separately in buffer solution (5 mM Tris-HCl/50 mM NaCl), at pH 7.2 were followed by agarose gel electrophoresis. The samples were incubated for 1 h at 37 °C. A loading buffer solution containing 25% bromophenol blue, 0.25% xylene cyanol, 30% glycerol was added and electrophoresis was carried out at 60 V for 1 h in Tris-HCl buffer using 1% agarose gel containing 1.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ethidium bromide. The reaction was monitored in presence of various radical inhibitors such as dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), ethanol (EtOH), sodium azide (NaN_3), groove binders; methyl green (MG) and 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI). The inhibition reactions were carried out by the addition of the reagents prior to the addition of the complexes. The samples were incubated for 2 h at 37 °C. The gels were visualized by photograph the fluorescence of intercalated ethidium bromide under a UV illuminator. The cleavage efficiency was measured by determining the ability of the complex to convert the supercoiled DNA (SC or Form I) to nicked circular form (NC or Form II) and linear form (LC or Form III).

Conclusion

The hexanuclear copper(II) complex **1** bind significantly as compared to trinuclear complex **2**. Synergistic effects of six copper(II) centers of complex **1** contributes significant DNA cleavage activity. The cationic property of the complex in aqueous solution may be another factor that contributes to the high activity. Active oxygen intermediates such as hydroxyl radicals and singlet oxygen may play an important role in the cleavage mechanism. Further investigations into the cleavage mechanism are

needed to develop more effective nucleases for this class of compounds.

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